

OPEN SEARCH USE CASES FOR IMPROVING INFORMATION DISCOVERY AND INFORMATION RETRIEVAL IN LARGE AND HIGHLY CONNECTED ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract

Retrieving the right information by navigating through different information channels has proven to be a prominent problem for organizations that produce massive quantities of data. This paper investigates ways to use open search methodologies to improve information retrieval and information discovery and reduce the need to navigate through different information channels in large organizations, based on experiences at CERN. The importance of connecting organizational private data and public data is emphasised, together with the importance of open information. Focusing on survey data from CERN research groups, analysis of user's habits, usage of communication and information channels, and information needs has been carried out. Based on the results of the analysis and literature survey a concept has been proposed that integrates aspects of open information and open search. The concept aims to improve existing information retrieval and information discovery processes and to reduce the number of tools and time engagement of an existing system at CERN and in general in large organizations.

Keywords: Open search strategy, Information Generation, Information Navigation, Organisation Innovation

INTRODUCTION

The amount of data produced by humans has been increasing year by year due to the fact that the world has become more data-driven. Every day people send emails, take photos, make videos, create documents, and use diverse techniques of data and information generation [1]. Answering the question "How much data do humans Generate?" is reasonably difficult to answer with any degree of precision. In 2017 it is estimated that humans generate 33 trillion gigabytes of information per minute. With 90% of the total stock of the world data generated in the past 2 years [2]. This increase in the generation of information has created challenges in managing large amount of information.

On average a user in an organization sends and receives 128.8 emails per day, out of which up to 24% contain additional information in the form of attachments [3,4]. Besides email companies use face-to-face meetings, broadcast media communications, mobile communication, electronic com-

munication, and written communication as a means to share knowledge and in terms generate information [5]. Based on research done by the Intel group, big data is linked to organisations that generate a median of 300 terabytes (TB) of data weekly. This study also showed that one-third of analyzed organizations works with more than 500 TB of data per week. These organizations process unstructured data sources and aim to integrate methods of data processing to convert the data into a structured form [6].

Overall studies indicated that the wider the search for knowledge is the higher the organization's innovation. This has led to conclusions that the development of information openness can stimulate innovative activities, creation of innovative approaches, and greater performance [8,9]. Previous studies have been inclined to demonstrate benefits that of openness in organizations. Recently studies have begun to stress the downsides of openness, which would justify why not many organizations have adopted the concept of openness [10,12]. One of the main disadvantages of an organization's openness is the risk of losing competitive advantage and leaking of private information [16]. A study of information technologies for knowledge sharing in large healthcare organizations has shown that large and well-funded organizations struggle to develop and maintain such complex systems [13].

One of the main issues with such large amount of information in organisations is how to effectively retrieve information and re-find information and messages when needed. This requires a powerful search index within the organization but also access to a great verity of information outside the organization. Plenty of tools have been created for these use cases, usually some of them are used simultaneously [11]. Searching for files in email conversations, searching for pieces of information in conversations, and the increase in information generation in organizations make it visible that there is a growing demand for tools that support information retrieval for large organizations.

This paper focuses on the analysis of communication, information search, and retrieval habits in large and knowledge-focused organizations, exemplary of CERN employees, to determine possible improvements in their daily workflows, and to investigate how open search concepts can improve such settings. First, we will analyze the behavior of CERN users by studying user surveys conducted by the IT department at CERN. The result of this analysis will detail the habits and information needs of CERN users. Second, we

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introduce concepts on how to use open search in big organizations and the benefits and drawbacks of open search. We then provide specific use cases for CERN, that display how open search can benefit the organization.

BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

This section focuses on surveying topics of information generation, knowledge sharing, and the privacy effects of openness in large organizations with regards to data collected from CERN surveys. Of the total 37057 users that work at CERN, 1232 users participated in the CERN survey. The users were staff, fellows, technical students, external users, etc. from various departments and working backgrounds [18].

Information Generation

Based on previous definitions, big data organizations are organizations that produce more than 500 TB of data per week. In the case of CERN, just the Large Hadron Collider generates 10 GB per second. Data produced by the collider is used for research, reports, visualization, in communication and more [25]. As seen in table 1, CERN employees also use various methods of communication and data sharing. Communication methods used at CERN are chat, email, face-to-face, phone, SMS, social media, where people used email the most followed with face-to-face meetings [18]. Apart from these different communication methodologies, CERN users have different hardware at their disposal, ranging from mobile phones, tablets, laptops to desktop PCs [18]. This all illustrates the magnitude of information generated by such an organization. Even though a lot of information is generated by organizations, information is only useful when it is stored and organized in a way that it can be used at an appropriate time [11]. Organizations see big data and big data analytics as a high priority in their IT environments. They rated improving data analytics capabilities as very important and improving data analytics capabilities as one of the most important tasks to face [6].

Table 1: IT Department User Survey Report: Which methods do you use to communicate with colleagues? [18]

Method of Communication	User Count
Email	1216
Face-To-Face	1015
Chat	585
Phone	575
SMS	170
Social Media	111

Knowledge Sharing

Information is shared, transferred, and transformed with remarkable velocity nowadays. This has created a need for efficient knowledge management for the information to be useful and accessible. Sharing knowledge in organizations

can help build a competitive advantage if the knowledge is managed adequately. In literature, knowledge sharing is also called voluntary dispersion of acquired experiences and skills and it makes employees capable to develop values, skills, and competencies. [15]. With the appearance of the internet and social media, information management and knowledge sharing have become more accessible, but shortages within these systems have also been emphasized. Shortages like misinformation, fake news, and dissemination of false information [11]. According to the CERN user survey, a high percentage of users share their knowledge and retrieve information first with the use of email, then face-to-face meetings, and ultimately with the use of the IT infrastructure (CERNSearch or CERNWebsite). Mostly used to share documents with colleagues is email, followed by cloud storage [18]. The distribution of the usage of these methods for document and knowledge sharing can be seen in 2.

Table 2: IT Department User Survey Report: How do you share documents with colleagues? [18]

Methods for sharing documentation	User Count
Via Email	899
Indico	479
Afs	455
CernBox	377
Dfs	318
Twiki	315
Other	237
Edms	196
Sharepoint	192
Cds	144
Eos	118
OnedriveSocialCernCh	44
No	25

In recent years CERN has been working on the concept of open science, which uses the principles of open data and open search, to make the research done at CERN more visible and acceptable to the general public. This solution for open science by CERN has made it easier to access research papers and to easily validate the information presented by those papers [25].

Open Innovation

Institutional knowledge is an aggregate of experiences, processes, data, expertise, values, and information of employees of an organization. It defines a company's history and can contain crucial trends, projects, perspectives and that define a company's history. Properly documenting and sharing institutional knowledge throughout the organization enables the organization to tackle various problems and daily routines [14]. However, when a problem cannot be solved using organization's current routines, the organization is forced to innovate by developing new knowledge. Organizations

search for alternative solutions to problems when existing routines and processes fail to produce results that match the organization's goals [10]. The drive to use external sources of information for innovation and extension of knowledge, pushes organizations to be open and distribute information to facilitate innovation [9, 19]. Open innovation can be defined as the use of purposive inflows and outflows of knowledge to stimulate internal innovation and to increase the demands for external use of innovation, respectively [21]. A principal idea in open innovation is that organizations should utilize information search outside the confines of their organization. Search for external knowledge is quite complicated and challenging, involving difficulties such as the tacitness, complexity, rivalry, and indivisibility of knowledge which may not be helpful to its discovery and transfer [7]. The survey of CERN newcomers and the technologies they use shows how CERN is adapting to new trends from the technological standpoint to reinforce innovation and knowledge sharing. This has also led to the integration of many different tools that have similar capabilities and intentions. The survey also revealed that users still prefer to use email to share documents compared with other methods, but there is an increasing trend of using cloud-based services for document sharing. Since 2019, the number of individuals using cloud-based document sharing has increased by 36%. In 2016, 5% of the overall users used chat as a preferred method of communicating with work colleagues, in 2020 it has increased to 22%. [17].

Importance of Privacy in Open Data

The goal of open innovation and open information is to increase accountability, transparency, and to provide new and efficient services. Before the information is made open, in general cases it is anonymized, with the intent to remove any personal identifiers from the data. With a higher degree of anonymization, the less useful the information is [23]. This fact gives leverage to the de-anonymization of data. Cases like the Massachusetts health data leak and Netflix credit card backtracing are just a few that represent the danger of open data [22]. For organizations not being open with information is the key to obtaining a competitive advantage [11]. CERN does not have the risk of losing the competitive advantage as other more business-oriented organizations, but it has to uphold a level of anonymization to protect its employees. Since most of the information at CERN is shared via email or face-to-face meetings, it is understandable that the risk for de-anonymization of data is prevailing. The survey shows that a large percentage of surveyed users do not prefer to use social media and avoid sharing personal information at the workspace. Out of 1232 users, 913 do not use social networking services for work and 55 users encrypt their files for security and privacy reasons [18].

Discussion

Large and highly connected organizations, such as CERN, prefer the use of emails and face-to-face meetings as their main communication and knowledge sharing method. Most

of CERN users use email for information discovery about their department and peer group [17]. Emails and face-to-face offer confidentiality and protect sensitive information, but limit the ease of access to information. When trying to access documents via email, it is necessary to execute at least two operations, to send an inquiry to an individual and wait for an extended period for feedback, depending on the availability of the other person. Face-to-face meetings can both reduce or extend the time needed to retrieve relevant information. All meeting participants have to be available for the meeting to take place, which needs time to organize. On the other hand, meeting in large organizations results in meeting minutes, which is a quick summary of the meeting. These produced documents can then be inspected and information can be retrieved easily. [24]. The drawback of face-to-face meetings is that a part of the information produced in meetings can get lost due to inefficient documentation practices. The documentation produced at face-to-face meetings is restricted to the group of individuals that attended the meeting. This brings difficulties in sharing information with individuals outside of the work-group or meeting group and retrieving information. With the option of searching open information, the wait duration for the feedback and information is reduced, it is not necessary to arrange meetings and wait for another individual to execute queries. Identical queries can be executed multiple times with no additional expenditure of resources. In order for the information produced in organizations to be usable by open search tools, it is necessary to structure and normalize it for search. This leads to a more reliable approach to information organization and standardization in organizations and the possibility to share the information in a more manageable way not only between organization members but also outside of the organization. Search ready open information can be grouped by interest groups, filtered by users according to their interests, recommended to users that share similar interests or shared between similar organizations. [8]. According to the CERN IT department study, most of the users use the CERN webpage and meetings for information discovery about CERN related information and events [17]. This behavior of searching for information within a specific group of users facilitates the creation of information bubbles. Information bubbles can be defined as digital echo chambers where users see content and posts that agree only with their preexisting beliefs. By making the information more accessible, open search tools enable the users to break the information bubble and to focus on information outside of their usual scope. In large organizations, users have to be trained to use a vast number of tools that have a similar purpose [11]. This is also accurate for CERN. Besides the tools for information discovery of data in their departments, about CERN and events at CERN, users use software for technical documentation, version control software, blogging software, survey software, video software, project management software, wiki software, and multiple hardware components. This generation of large amounts of data complicates the process of keeping track of communication and information, not only for internal

Figure 1: Conceptual Integration Diagram of the Open Search System

purposes but also for external. Enabling individuals inside and outside the organization, groups, and organizations to consume and share the generated information is a basis point for enabling open innovation and increasing the value of the produced information. Taking into consideration the large amount of information that is continuously being generated, it is understandable that innovative methods for organization, aggregation, storing, and use of this information are needed. Organizations have to solve the problem of cost-effective storage of information and avoid information loss while taking into account privacy concerns. To make the stored information available and useful, methods for instant and reliable information retrieval and information discovery are needed. These methods have the goal to enable the validation of new information, improvement of access to existing information, improvement of existing processes, creation of new processes, and promotion of innovation and transparency.

TOWARDS A CONSOLIDATED RETRIEVAL EXPERIENCE

Based on the research from the previous chapter, we have seen that innovation and user productivity is linked to the level and ease of access to information. We propose an open search solution that enables the search and sharing of private and public information within the organization but also enables users outside of organizations access to organizations' public data. The concept system needs to enable easy access to multidimensional data aggregated from multiple information sources. These information sources are not only sources within the organization but also relevant information outside of the organization's documents, emails, meeting notes, etc. Figure 1 shows a

conceptual integration diagram of the open search system, that acts as a medium for different kinds of users and information. The system has to enable the organizational user access to internal private and public organization knowledge depending on the rights, but also the ability to discover external information. In order to facilitate innovation and to share organizational data that is relevant to the general public, it is also necessary to enable the external user access to public organizational data. The concept system needs to meet the following requirements:

- Storage of large amounts of private and public data while taking into consideration privacy concerns
- Aggregation of different data sources (within an organization or outside sources) and normalization of data
- Implementation of the open data concept
- Intuitive access to information for internal and external users
- Restrictions of access to private information
- Possibility to share information within an organization or outside of an organization
- Ability to search for internal and external information

In the case of CERN, to avoid data loss by using multiple tools for information and document sharing, concentrating information into email communication and sharing with individuals via face-to-face, we propose a concept where public and private data is normalized and saved into secure data storage. It is necessary to distinguish between private and public data. Private data at CERN is classified as data that is accessible for one group of users or as data that need additional rights to be accessed. Data that is produced by CERN or external sources and is accessible by the public

or CERN employees without any protection is classified as public data. The normalized public and private data should be indexed and prepared for search. Having the data in an open format and ready for information retrieval and discovery fulfills the requirements for the use of open search. The main benefits of open search can be seen in the fact that the organizational information and external information would be available at any point in time, that is information retrieval is not dependent on the availability of another individual as with face-to-face meetings and email conversation. The information would not be restricted to the mailbox of an individual since it is made open and accessible. Since the data is not kept private per person or department, inter-department information exchange is made possible. Easier access to information improves the competences of organizational users. Besides easier access to information, time spent on information retrieval and resources spent on face-to-face meetings have the potential to be reduced significantly.

The benefits of this system in a general case would be, as presented previously, just-in-time access to information, validation of data sources of the information, the ability to extend the search to other departments or to execute an external search and the reduction of tools and time effort needed to retrieve relevant information. Enabling access to information outside of the organization is beneficial for users or other organizations with similar interests that are not in the organization. It also provides a way of information validation outside of the organization.

SUMMARY AND FUTURE WORK

We have described the extent of information that is generated on a daily basis by individuals and organizations, with a focus on the generation of data by CERN. This has been the base for the introduction of knowledge management, open innovation, and open information. Privacy issues with regards to open data and open search have been presented. Results from user surveys from CERN have been analyzed and users' information needs, together with their habits have been determined. Based on these results, an open information-based search system has been proposed and future ideas for the system have been suggested.

There are many technical challenges that need to be addressed to make open search and open information in large organizations a more complete and useful tool for information discovery and information retrieval. The technical challenges vary from organization processes and storage of the information to data combination and data retrieval. Other than technical challenges, issues with user privacy, and user rights need to be analyzed in-depth.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the integration of open information and implementation of open search methodologies on large datasets from large organizations have the potential to improve the competences of organizational users and increase the competitive advantage of an organization while reducing the

effort and time needed for the process of information discovery and information retrieval. Providing access to an organization's public data to the public is beneficial for information validation of the organization.

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